

Student-Built Dream Teachers: A Student-Led Agentic AI Framework for Personalized Learning

Pavan Goyal ^{†1}

¹Blue Blocks Montessori School

²Blue Blocks Micro Research Institute

May 25, 2026

Abstract

The present study provides a student-centric framework to create personalized AI tutors by leveraging learner preferences mapping with Large Language Models. Unlike traditional and “hardcoded” educational chatbots, students can create their own version of a tutor that aligns with the desired personality, manner of communication, level of emotional support, teaching approach and motivational behavior. Before building the prototype, a 30-question survey was individually completed by 12 students (aged 12–16) in order to collect students’ classroom preferences, emotional learning needs, and expectation for their ideal AI tutor. The obtained student preferences were then used by the students to create individual teacher preference profiles, which were converted into prompted instructions for behaviors through the Anthropic Claude API. Using these self-defined preferences, the students built a simple AI tutor prototype on a web interface with the use of Python and Streamlit, under facilitator guidance, so students could interact with an AI shaped by their own chosen traits and learning style. This framework shifted from a “one size fits all” teaching style toward an emotion-aware, student-driven AI tutor. The data also illustrates that students were able to take part in creating their own AI learning environments with relevant details; it was evident that emotion-safety, the need for building confidence, and engaging teaching styles were desired among multiple students profiles and likely future AI teachers will need to cater to the emotional as well as knowledge aspects of learning; work shows the framework to be practical and applicable in the school environment.

1 Introduction

Personalised learning has been increasingly recognised as being highly desirable and useful [2, 11]. As learners do not only differ in their academic abilities but in their learning styles, and how they like to be taught, supported and guided. The single human teacher finds it a challenge to cater to all of the students in the class; be that through meeting their communication needs, their learning styles or their emotional needs [8, 7, 10]. Some students require calm and patient explanations, while others prefer to be taught using humour, a challenge, or storytelling in a friendly and relaxed manner. Thus, educational tools need to accommodate deeper adaptations to the learner. This project describes the use of a student-centred approach to educational artificial intelligence where the student co-creates their own AI teacher [4, 3, 9]. Instead of students being presented with a general AI tutor; they are first presented with 30 questions designed to ascertain the students’ emotions, their teacher preferences, comfort with communication style, their need for motivation, and preferred style of explanation. These questions are intended not only to learn about the student, but for the student to find out what kind of teacher is useful to them. A total of 12 students (aged between 12-16) were involved in the study; each student used their own responses to create a preference profile of the desired personality, behavior and teaching style for their ideal AI

teacher, and these profiles were used by the students to generate a personalized AI teacher for each of them. To carry out the process the students used the API from Claude [1] to generate the individual AI teacher prototypes [1]. The simple agentic AI prototype was built by the students using Python in VS Code and was deployed as a web page through Streamlit, with facilitator guidance where required [6]. Thus, the student does not only act as the user of an AI; but also, the creator of a bespoke teaching agent with choices based on learning style. The system therefore seeks to transcend that of a simple chatbot toward that of a truly agentic, emotionally-attuned, and student-directed learning environment [9, 3]. By co-designing the teacher the project seeks a human-centred approach to AI in education which is shaped not only by subject matter, but also by emotion and a student’s agency [8, 2].

2 Data

2.1 Study Design and Participants

The primary purpose of this study was to comprehend how students in school preferred to be taught in terms of their emotional, behavioral and academic preferences so that the study later helped students translate these preferences into individualized profiles for AI teacher characteristics. Specifically, the aim was to gather how a learner wanted their

teacher to be in terms of their personality, communication style, emotional support and the way they teach. 12 students took part in the survey from 12-16 years old and had the following grades: Grade 7 Vihan, Amaira, Pratheetha, Varun, Kartikeya, Aahan, Ranbir, Vedika; Grade 9 Ashrith, Saachi, Ummehani and Grade 10 Sreshta (IGCSE). Each student individually completed the questionnaire so that every answer given was a student's own preference, choice and their personal emotional learning preference and not influenced by peers. The questionnaire was a formal preference-mapping instrument composed of 30 questions and each question asked was multiple choice.

The overall questionnaire was divided into five thematic sections:

- Section 1: How you feel in class
- Section 2: Your dream teacher's personality
- Section 3: How your teacher should talk
- Section 4: What you need emotionally
- Section 5: Your AI teacher preferences

The purpose of this design was to help students convert their own responses into meaningful learner profiles that could later guide the behaviour, personality, and response style of the AI teacher they built.

2.2 Questionnaire-Based Data Collection

The primary dataset for this study was collected through a 30-question structured questionnaire. The questions were designed to capture student preferences across classroom behaviour, teacher personality, communication style, emotional learning needs, and AI teacher expectations.

The complete question set used for data collection is listed below.

Section 1: How You Feel in Class

1. How do you feel when you do not understand something the teacher explains?
2. How often do you ask questions in class?
3. What stops you from asking questions in class?
4. When your teacher explains something in a boring way, what do you do?
5. How do you feel when your teacher calls on you to answer in front of the class?
6. How do you feel after your teacher praises you in front of the class?

Section 2: Your Dream Teacher's Personality

7. Which personality type do you want most in a teacher?
8. When you give a wrong answer, how should your ideal teacher respond?
9. When you give a brilliant answer, how should your ideal teacher react?
10. When you feel like giving up on a hard topic, what should your teacher do?

11. What kind of relationship do you want with your AI teacher?
12. How much humour do you want from your teacher?

Section 3: How Your Teacher Should Talk

13. Which speaking style do you prefer from your teacher?
14. How should your teacher explain a difficult concept?
15. How long should your teacher's answers be?
16. When explaining science or math, which examples feel most relatable to you?
17. How should your teacher get your attention at the start of a lesson?

Section 4: What You Need Emotionally

18. What makes you feel safe to learn?
19. What makes you feel understood by a teacher?
20. What motivates you the most to keep learning?
21. When you are frustrated with a topic, what do you need?
22. How aware do you want your teacher to be of your emotions?
23. What kind of recognition matters most to you?

Section 5: Your AI Teacher Preferences

24. If your AI teacher was a character, who would it be most like?
25. What tone should your AI teacher's voice or text feel like?
26. Which subjects do you most want your AI teacher to cover?
27. How should your AI teacher handle a topic it does not know?
28. How often would you want to use your AI teacher?
29. What is the one thing you want your AI teacher to help you with the most?
30. After using an AI teacher, what would make you feel it was worth it?

The collected responses formed the core dataset of the study. Since the answers were gathered independently and in a structured multiple-choice format, they were suitable for later conversion into student-specific AI teacher profiles. These profiles were then used by the students to define preferred teaching tone, emotional support style, explanation strategy, and overall AI teacher personality for their own AI tutor prototypes. The entire dataset with the questionnaire, responses and chat with Claude is available on Harvard Dataverse [5].

3 Methodology

3.1 Overview of the Methodological Pipeline

The methodology for this project was devised in order to take student preference information and allow students to generate a tailor-made AI teacher. This pipeline consists of four parts; (1) a survey with 30 questions used to get a student’s response, (2) students interpret each response into a student teacher preference profile, (3) students turn this teacher preference profile into prompt based AI teacher instructions, (4) students implement the final AI teacher using a web app interface programmed with Python and Streamlit, with facilitator guidance where required. The whole point of the methodology was to not have students talk to pre-existing chatbot, but to shape and build each AI teacher’s personality, tonality, behavior and teaching approach by the results that the students get from the 30 question survey.

3.2 Preference-to-Prompt Design

Once the questionnaire phase was completed, the replies of each individual student were interpreted by the students as a preference profile which included desired teacher characteristics in relation to: emotional support; degree of humour; way of providing correction; method of explanation; way of speaking; tone; and overall teacher personality. The next step in the methodology was the translation of the profile characteristics into instructions for the prompt. This involved the transformation of the relevant questionnaire patterns into natural-language behavioural rules that could be sent to Claude, in the form of a system prompt. For example, if a student’s response indicated a desire for a wise mentor, the student prompt emphasized patience, guidance, and the appropriate teacher tone, whereas a student who wanted the teacher to use pop-culture references, jokes and short, entertaining explanations would have those preferences directly indicated in the student prompt, creating a behavioral conditioning of the AI teacher.

3.3 Implementation Using Claude API

The personalized AI teacher was implemented by the students using Anthropic’s Claude API, with facilitator guidance where required. In the code structure, the Claude model was accessed through the `anthropic` Python library, and the API client was initialized using a user-supplied API key [1]. The model configuration was kept modular through a dedicated `MODEL` variable, allowing easy switching between different Claude model versions depending on speed, capability, or cost.

A key methodological component of the implementation was the `TEACHER_PERSONALITY` block. This was a long natural-language system prompt that defined the teacher’s core traits, teaching style, knowledge coverage, and behavioural constraints. This block functioned as the main teacher-conditioning instruction. In the present prototype, it defined `BLUE` as a compassionate, adaptive, motivating, knowledgeable, and engaging AI teacher. It also specified how explanations should be given, how humour should be used, how curiosity should be encouraged, and how inappropriate or irrelevant queries should be redirected back to educational topics.

In a generalized research version of the methodology, this teacher personality block can be customized per student by replacing the generic teacher description with student-specific behavioural instructions derived from the questionnaire. Therefore, the student-built implementation demonstrates a scalable architecture for transforming student preference profiles into individualized system prompts.

3.4 Web-Based Deployment Through Streamlit

The deployment layer of the student-built system was built using Streamlit. Streamlit was selected because it allows rapid creation of interactive web interfaces directly from Python code, making it suitable for educational prototyping and student-led development.

The deployed interface consisted of three main components:

- a front-end chat area for student–AI interaction,
- a session-based memory structure for storing the running conversation,
- a sidebar-based control panel for model display, memory reset, and teacher configuration instructions.

The code used `st.chat_input()` to receive student queries and `st.chat_message()` to display both student and AI teacher responses. The conversation history was stored using `st.session_state.messages`, which allowed the model to respond in a multi-turn conversational format rather than as isolated single-question outputs. This provided a lightweight conversational memory within each active session.

The interface was also intentionally styled with a futuristic visual theme using custom CSS. Although this styling does not alter the core language model logic, it plays an important methodological role in user experience design. The aesthetic framing of the AI teacher as a futuristic educational companion may affect engagement, emotional attachment, and the student’s willingness to interact repeatedly with the system.

3.5 Response Generation Logic

Once a student entered a query through the Streamlit interface, the system appended the query to the session message history. The code then sent the full chat history, together with the teacher-conditioning system prompt, to the Claude API. The language model generated a response conditioned on both the conversation and the predefined teacher personality.

The output pipeline therefore followed the following operational sequence:

1. The student enters a query in the web interface.
2. The query is stored in the session conversation history.
3. The Claude API is called using the selected model.
4. The `TEACHER_PERSONALITY` prompt is supplied as the system instruction.
5. The stored conversation history is passed as the message context.

6. Claude generates a response consistent with the instructed teacher style.
7. The response is displayed in the chat interface and appended to the session history.

This makes the system prompt-driven, state-aware, and easily modifiable. From a methodological perspective, this architecture is valuable because it allows students to rapidly test different teacher personalities and instructional designs without changing the underlying model itself.

3.6 Scientific Role of the Code Structure

The code can be interpreted as consisting of five scientific-functional layers:

1. **Configuration Layer:** stores API key, model choice, and student-defined teacher behaviour instructions.
2. **Personality Conditioning Layer:** defines the pedagogical identity of the AI teacher through a system prompt.
3. **Interface Layer:** provides the student-facing interaction environment through Streamlit.
4. **Conversation State Layer:** stores running messages using session state to preserve short-term context.
5. **Inference Layer:** sends the prompt and conversation to Claude and retrieves the generated response.

This layered design is important because it separates educational design choices from core inference logic. As a result, student teacher preferences can be modified by editing the conditioning instructions rather than rewriting the entire application.

3.7 Methodological Significance

The approach is important because it combines both the explicit education preference mapping with the implicit prompt-based LM personalization. The student identifies and specifies their desired teacher type and the student-built implementation translates that wish into a behavior that the AI exhibits, by naturally language conditioning the model’s responses. The system, is more than just a generic chatbot, instead acting as a student-dictated teaching agent. In the described study, the methodology is used and shown as a realistic low-barrier way to enable personalized AI teaching through student questionnaires, profile analysis, prompt design, integration of Claude API and Streamlit app deployment that is perfect for fast prototyping within a school environment, and could be extended in future research through storing profiles, including long-term memory, analytics, per student automated prompts.

3.8 Methodology Flowchart

The overall methodological pipeline of the proposed system is illustrated in Figure 1. It summarizes how student questionnaire responses were transformed by the students into personalized AI teacher behaviour through prompt design, Claude API integration, and Streamlit-based deployment.

4 Discussion

These results provide evidence that students designing and building AI teachers not only can be technically successful but can also create meaningful AI teachers educationally. Even though there were individual variations in student age, confidence, classroom demeanor, and preferred mode of communication there were consistent similarities in a range of student responses. The most common overlap identified was the feeling of emotional security necessary in the learning process. For many students it was important that their AI teacher did not make them feel afraid of the consequences of getting an answer wrong, that they be “kind to their mistakes,” and that learning be comfortable and feel safe enough to ask questions. This is clearly not just a supplementary request but is an essential one.

A second major overlap was the desire for confidence-building support. Across multiple student profiles, the AI teacher was expected not just to explain content, but to help learners believe in themselves, remain motivated, and gradually become more secure in difficult subjects. For a number of these instances, students expressed the value they saw in gaining confidence is equal to, and sometimes greater than, immediate academic correctness. These examples suggest that an AI teacher may take on a more comprehensive role within a school environment than simply explaining content: helping students believe in themselves and build resilience. The third domain of intersecting interests were students’ interest in having their instructions be fun and engaging. Many of the students described enjoying learning if their tutor included jokes, stories, pop culture references, personal experience or friendly chatter. The evidence that fun and learning are not mutually exclusive, and perhaps students even consider their tutor to be more effective if it is fun, demonstrate the students’ desire for an AI that is not just factual and machine-like, but active and personable. However, in spite of these similarities between student desires, the data also showed major differences between them. Some students wished for an AI teacher that was a calm, mentor-like presence, while others wanted an AI that was more playful, friendly, and engaging. Some students wanted short, brief explanations, others wanted lengthy, step-by-step guidance. Some students wanted the AI to be highly emotionally intelligent, whereas others valued the accuracy and quality of the lesson over any emotional engagement. These individual differences reinforce the initial hypothesis that there is not one AI personality that works for all students, and that the tool must be personalizable.

Figure 2 highlights the overlaps in the three of the most frequent themes in the student profiles: emotional safety, building confidence, and fun/engagement. The overlapping portion is indicative of how many of the students were not interested in solely having a teacher who addressed just one of these characteristics; rather, they wanted an AI teacher who would address these three areas simultaneously.

Overall, the conversation is indicative that a student-created and developed AI teacher can be a productive model to consider in future learning technology. By allowing students to guide and create the personality of the AI teacher, they move beyond merely receiving system recommendations to actively co-creating their learning agent. This allows the AI to better address the students’ emotional and pedagogical needs and move beyond a chatbot model toward a truly adaptive agent.

Figure 1: Detailed end-to-end methodological pipeline of the student-designed and student-built agentic AI teacher framework.

Overlapping Emotional-Learning Themes Across Student Profiles

Figure 2: Overlap of the three dominant recurring themes across student profiles: emotional safety, confidence building, and fun/engagement.

5 Conclusion

This study presented a student-centered approach to designing and building personalized AI teachers using a 30-question preference questionnaire, Claude API[1], Python, and Streamlit. The responses of 12 students aged 12 to 16 were converted by the students into individual teacher preference profiles, which were then used to shape the behaviour and style of the AI teacher.

The findings show that students can meaningfully contribute to the design and construction of their own AI learning systems. Rather than using a generic chatbot, they were able to define and build the kind of teacher they wanted, including qualities such as kindness, humour, patience, confidence-building support, and mentor-like guidance.

Overall, the study highlights the potential of student-built AI teachers as a practical step toward more human-centered and adaptive educational technology. The repeated overlap of emotional safety, confidence building, and engaging teaching style suggests that future AI teaching systems should focus not only on explaining content, but also on how students emotionally experience learning.

6 Data Availability and Authenticity

The data used in this experiment belong to Blue Blocks Montessori School, Hyderabad, India. All data are real-world data collected in a real-world educational scenario. The questionnaire, student responses, and Claude interaction data are available through Harvard Dataverse [5]. The dataset DOI is <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/PEMXKT>.

References

[1] Anthropic. Claude 3.5 sonnet model card. <https://www.anthropic.com/news/claude-3-5-sonnet>, 2024. Large language model.

[2] Oyebola Olusola Ayeni, Nancy Mohd Al Hamad, Onyebuchi Nneamaka Chisom, Blessing Osawaru, and Olo-

lade Elizabeth Adewusi. Ai in education: A review of personalized learning and educational technology. *GSC Advanced Research and Reviews*, 18(2):261–271, 2024.

[3] Sankalan Pal Chowdhury, Vilém Zouhar, and Mrinmaya Sachan. Autotutor meets large language models: A language model tutor with rich pedagogy and guardrails. In *Proceedings of the Eleventh ACM Conference on Learning @ Scale, L@S '24*, pages 5–15. Association for Computing Machinery, 2024.

[4] Silvia García-Méndez, Francisco de Arriba-Pérez, and María del Carmen Somoza-López. A review on the use of large language models as virtual tutors. *Science & Education*, 34(2):877–892, 2025.

[5] Pavan Goyal. Designing the Dream Teacher: A Student-Centered Agentic AI Framework for Personalized Learning (DataSet), 2026.

[6] Mohammad Khorasani, Mohamed Abdou, and J Hernández Fernández. Web application development with streamlit. *Software Development*, 498:507, 2022.

[7] Angeline Lillard and Nicole Else-Quest. Evaluating montessori education. *Science*, 313(5795):1893–1894, 2006.

[8] Angeline S. Lillard. *Montessori: The Science Behind the Genius*. Oxford University Press, 2005.

[9] Yuxin Liu, Zeqing Song, Jiong Lou, Chentao Wu, and Jie Li. Agenttutor: Empowering personalized learning with multi-turn interactive teaching in intelligent education systems. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2601.04219*, 2025.

[10] Chloë Marshall. Montessori education: A review of the evidence base. *npj Science of Learning*, 2(1):11, 2017.

[11] Minju Park, Sojung Kim, Seunghyun Lee, Soonwoo Kwon, and Kyuseok Kim. Empowering personalized learning through a conversation-based tutoring system with student modeling. In *Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pages 1–10, 2024.